

Interview Protocol

Introductory Protocol

Thank you for attending this session. To facilitate note-taking, we would like to record our conversations today. For your information, only researchers on the project will be privy to the recording which will be destroyed by the end of the project and after they are transcribed. In addition, you must sign a form that essentially states that: (1) all information will be held confidential, (2) your participation is voluntary and you may stop at any time if you feel uncomfortable, and (3) we do not intend to inflict any harm. Thank you for agreeing to participate.

We have planned this interview to last no longer than one hour. During this time, we have several questions that we would like to cover. If time begins to run short, it may be necessary to interrupt you in order to push ahead and complete this line of questioning.

Session Introduction

You have been selected to speak with us today because your role represented the organization. This interview aims to investigate values implementation in agile software development organizations. Our research project as a whole focuses on the role of values in agile software development organizations. We are trying to learn about the importance of values from practitioners perspective and how values can be integrated into day-to-day agile software development.

There will be four parts in our session today. You are not limited in answering the questions, unless specified. Your elaborate answer is valuable for us. Do you have any questions or concerns before we begin? Then, with your permission we will begin the interview.

A. Organization's Value

Are the organization values considered in the Agile software development process?

If so, how?

Probes: Any tool or framework? Which agile phase or ceremony? Which agile artifact is involved?

How do you measure the organization's value that is being integrated?

Probes: What metrics did you use? Any tool or framework?

B. Organization Perception of Employee Value

Is your organization concerned about how the human values of the employees affect their decision-making or practices in agile software development?

If so, how is that considered in the Agile software development process?

If not, why not?

C. Organization Perception of Social Sustainability

[Show the social sustainability values]

Which social sustainability values are the most relevant with your product and domain you are working on? Choose the top three. Probes: Why?

Are there any mechanisms from your organization to ensure social sustainability values inclusion in day-to-day agile?

Probes: If yes, how? Could you elaborate it in the agile software development context? If not, why? What is the challenge?

Session Ending

Thank you for your participation today. This session will be transcribed by the researchers. The result will be sent to the respective participant, if desired. Do you have any questions or concerns before we end the session? If you have any questions or concerns later, you may contact us.